

Thermal simulation of human body-clothing-environment system

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Introduction

In the recent past, thermal comfort of the clothing has been becoming one of the most important aspect for the customers, and therefore also for the researchers. The thermal comfort of human body is a complex issue and is affected by the physical (e.g. heat and mass transfer, mechanical behaviour of the textile), physiological (e.g. sensory and thermoregulatory responses), psychological (e.g. wearing comfort, perception of the various sensations) processes which occur in the environment-human-clothing system [1]. Therefore, the designing of outdoor and protective clothing that not only offer the ergonomic but also thermo-physiological wear comfort, is a difficult and time consuming task. Hence, researchers are shifting towards the virtual modelling to achieve their goal without having chaotic prototyping process. Most of the simulations have been done for the fit and the ergonomic wear comfort of the garment and virtually no computer-assisted solutions exist for the realistic prediction of thermal comfort. The cross-linking of both approaches therefore requires extensive research. The objectives of this work are to analyse the heat regulation among human body, microclimate, clothing, and environment and to develop application-oriented principles and processes for the simulation of outdoor clothing according to geometrical, textile-physical and thermal parameters.

Method and results

In order to simulate the heat regulation between human body-clothing-environment, 3D model of a human body was generated by using 3D scanner VITUS [2] and the software *Geomagic* [3] for processing and refining the scanned data. Subsequently, this 3D model was assigned the properties of the Fiala Model [4] by using the software *Theseus-FE* [5]. This generated human model (Figure 1) that is based on individual scan data can now perform active and passive thermoregulations.

Figure 1: a: Thermophysiological model in Theseus-FE left: surface model, right: body elements [6][7]; b: Thermophysiological model based on individual data

According to the selected design, 2D pattern development and as well 3D fit simulation of a jacket with three different fits (slim, normal, loose) were done by using the software *Modaris V8* [7] (Figure 2). Fit and thermal simulation depend on the material properties. Therefore, the physical, mechanical and thermal properties of the selected textile material were comprehensively analysed. The air gaps that are developed by draping between clothing and the human body have a significant influence on heat regulation and thermal comfort. The air gaps were divided into different air-zones with respect to the thickness and location on the body.

Figure 2: (a) 2D Patterns of the normal fit jacket, (b) 3D fit simulation of the jacket with three different fits

As, each air-zone has a different heat transfer coefficient h due to thickness and length. Therefore the heat transfer coefficient of each air-zone was calculated by $h = \frac{\overline{Nu}_L k}{L}$ [8]:

Here, Nu_L is the Nusselt number, which is the function of Prandtl and Rayleigh number, L is the characteristics length, k is the conductivity. After defining the thermal properties of the textile material (heat capacity, clothing insulation, evaporative resistance) and the boundary conditions in *Theseus-FE*, the heat regulation of body-clothing-environment system was simulated. Figure 3 shows the results of the thermal simulation for three different fits. This innovative approach gives the researchers the opportunity to analyse the combined effects of body shape, clothing design, and environmental conditions on the heat regulation of the human body.

Figure 3: a: Surface temperature of body and jacket during thermal simulation after 6600 sec; b: Temperature of body surface at thorax up anterior during the simulation

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